

IMPACT OF BIOSTIMULANT TREATMENTS ON LEAF DEVELOPMENT IN VARIOUS SOYBEAN CULTIVARS

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Abstract. This article presents data on the effects of applying the biostimulants “Uz Gumin” and “Fitovak” as well as the biopreparation “Yer Malhami” on the formation of leaf number in soybean plants of the “Nafis” (local) and “Vilana” (foreign) cultivars. Treatments were applied before sowing and during the budding, flowering, and pod formation stages. Field experiment results revealed that each biostimulant had a different level of impact on leaf organ formation. Notably, the application of “Yer Malhami” resulted in the formation of 36.7 leaves in the “Nafis” cultivar and 36.6 leaves in the “Vilana” cultivar during the pod formation stage, exceeding the control by 4.1 and 5.7 leaves, respectively. The application of “Fitovak” during all three growth stages also demonstrated high effectiveness, significantly increasing the number of leaves.

Keywords: Soybean, Biostimulants, Uz Gumin, Fitovak, Yer malhami, Nafis and Vilana cultivars, number of leaves, vegetation period

Аннотация. В данной статье представлены данные о влиянии применения биостимуляторов «Уз гумин», «Фитовак» и биопрепарата «Ер малхамии» на формирование количества листьев у сортов сои «Нафис» (местный) и «Вилана» (зарубежный) при обработке семян до посева, а также в фазах бутонизации, цветения и формирования стручков. Результаты полевых исследований показали, что каждый из биостимуляторов по-разному влияет на формирование листовых органов растения. В частности, применение биопрепарата «Ер малхамии» в фазе формирования стручков привело к образованию 36,7 листьев у сорта «Nafis» и 36,6 листьев у сорта «Вилана», что на 4,1-5,7 листьев больше по сравнению с контролем. Также установлено, что трёхэтапное применение биостимулятора «Фитовак» демонстрирует высокую эффективность и способствует значительному увеличению количества листьев.

Ключевые слова: Соя, Биостимуляторы, Уз гумин, Фитовак, Ер малхамии Сорта сои Nafis и Vilana, количество листьев, Вегетационный период

Introduction. Soybean (*Glycine max*) is one of the most widely cultivated and economically important crops in the world. Currently, soybean is grown in 104 countries on approximately 120.5 million hectares annually, yielding more than 333.7 million tons of production. This translates to an average of 50 kilograms of soybeans per capita in soybean-producing countries. According to international statistics, global soybean production was projected to increase by 11% in 2022-2023 due to the expansion of soybean cultivation areas in South America, with total production expected to reach 389 million tons. However, in recent years, global soybean yields have shown a declining trend. This situation highlights the urgent need for scientific research focused on developing new soybean cultivars that are resistant to climate change, drought, diseases, pests, and insects, as well as on implementing innovative technologies that promote resource-efficient cultivation practices [1].

Review of the Literature. The leaf is one of the primary organs of plants and is actively involved in key physiological processes such as photosynthesis, respiration, and transpiration. A leaf typically consists of three main parts: (1) the petiole, which attaches the leaf to the stem; (2) the leaf blade, which constitutes the main body of the leaf; and (3) the leaf base, which firmly connects the leaf to the stem. The morphological, anatomical, and ecological characteristics of leaves play a crucial role in helping plants adapt to their environmental conditions and support their growth and development. Furthermore, leaves are not only essential for individual plant function but also hold significant importance for the entire ecosystem, contributing to ecological stability and playing an active role in atmospheric gas exchange [8].

As A.A. Nichiporovich emphasized, “achieving high yields means establishing a system that ensures the efficient use of photosynthesis, which is the primary function of green plants” Therefore, in crop production, particular attention is paid to the number of leaves, their development, and total leaf surface area [3].

The formation of organic matter in plants results from the physiological activity of chlorophyll granules in the leaves, in conjunction with the absorption of essential mineral nutrients through the root system [9].

Up to 95% of the total organic matter accumulated in plants is attributed to the photosynthesis process that occurs in the leaves, while only 5-10% is associated with root activity. Since photosynthesis takes place in the leaves, it is critically important to assess how agrotechnological practices influence leaf development. During photosynthesis, approximately 80-90% of the plant's

biological yield potential is formed. Therefore, plant growth, development, and productivity are directly dependent on the efficiency of the photosynthetic process [2].

Research Conditions and Methodology. Field experiments were conducted at the educational and research experimental farm of Tashkent State Agrarian University. The experimental site is located in Qibray district, Tashkent region, on the right bank of the Chirchiq River, at an altitude of 550-570 meters above sea level.

The soil of the experimental farm is classified as typical irrigated sierozem, which has been traditionally irrigated for many years.

The experiment included 20 variants, each arranged in 4 rows, with a row spacing of 70 cm. The area of each experimental plot was 70 m², measuring 2.8 meters in width and 25 meters in length. Of this, 35 m² was used for data collection. The total experimental area was 4,200 m². The variants were arranged in a randomized design with three replications.

The research was carried out under both field and laboratory conditions, using the methodologies outlined in “Methods of Conducting Field Experiments” (UzPITI) [4], B. Dospekhov’s “Methodology of Field Experiments” [6], and the “Methodology of State Variety Testing of Agricultural Crops” [5]. In addition, the methods described in “Methods of Agrochemical and Agrophysical Research of Soils in Central Asia” were applied. For determining leaf surface area, Nichiporovich’s gravimetric method was used, and for assessing the number and weight of nodules, the method developed by G.S. Posipankov [7] was employed.

Research Results. Based on the results of the research conducted during the study year, the effect of various biostimulants on the number of leaves and their formation during different vegetative stages (bud formation, flowering, and pod development) was examined in soybean plants of the “Nafis” and “Vilana” varieties. Each biostimulant was applied according to different treatment schemes: seed treatment before sowing (ml/t or l/t), and foliar spraying during bud formation, flowering, and pod formation stages (ml/ha or l/ha). In the control variant, no biostimulants were applied, and these samples were evaluated as background indicators of plant physiology without any treatment effects.

In the control variant of the “Nafis” variety, an average of 4.8 leaves were observed during the bud formation stage, 19.8 leaves during flowering, and 32.6 leaves during the pod development stage. These values reflect the biological potential of the variety in the absence of any biostimulant application.

Application of the biostimulant “Uz Gumin” at a rate of 300 ml/t for seed treatment, 500 ml/ha during the bud formation stage, and 800 ml/ha during the flowering pod formation stages led to an increase in the number of leaves. It was found that during the bud formation stage, an average of 5.3 leaves were formed; during flowering, 21.5 leaves; and during pod development, 34.0 leaves per plant. This indicates a notable increase in leaf number at each stage compared to the control: 0.5 more leaves during bud formation, 2.0 more during flowering, and 1.4 more during pod development.

When the biostimulant “Fitovak” was applied only as a seed treatment at a rate of 200 ml/t, the following results were observed: an average of 5.2 leaves formed during the bud formation stage, 21.0 during flowering, and 33.7 during the pod formation stage. These indicators were close to those obtained from the application of “Uz Gumin”, demonstrating that even seed-only treatment with “Fitovak” had a significant impact. This suggests that “Fitovak” has the potential to influence the plant’s internal metabolism from the early stages of development.

Moreover, when “Fitovak” was applied in a combined scheme 200 ml/t on seeds and 300 ml/ha during the bud formation stage the results were even more pronounced: 5.6 leaves were observed during bud formation, 21.8 during flowering, and 34.3 during pod formation. During the flowering stage alone, this represented an increase of 2.3 leaves compared to the control.

In the three-stage application scheme of the “Fitovak” biostimulant, the highest results were recorded: when applied at a rate of 200 ml/t to the seeds, 300 ml/ha at the budding stage, and 500 ml/ha during the flowering and pod formation stages, the number of leaves formed was 5.9 during budding, 23.0 during flowering, and 35.6 during pod formation. This indicates that multi-stage and complex application of the biostimulant has a positive effect on the development of leaf organs in the plant.

The “Yer malhami” biopreparation also demonstrated high efficacy during the experiment. When applied at a rate of 2.0 l/t to the seeds, the results were as follows: 5.4 leaves at the budding stage, 21.6 leaves at flowering, and 34.4 leaves at pod formation. When the biopreparation was applied to the seeds (2.0 l/t), at the budding stage (2.0 l/ha), and again during flowering and pod formation stages (2.0 l/ha), even higher results were achieved: 5.9 leaves during budding, 23.9 during flowering, and 36.7 during pod formation.

During the 2023 field experiments, the formation of leaves in the “Vilana” soybean variety was analyzed under the influence of different biostimulants

(“Uz gumin”, “Fitovak”) and the biopreparation (“Yer malhami”). Under experimental conditions, each biostimulant was applied in different combinations: seed treatment only, as well as during the budding, flowering, and pod formation stages. Based on the collected data, the morphological changes of this variety were thoroughly analyzed.

In the control variant, where no biostimulants were applied, the “Vilana” soybean variety formed an average of 4.1 leaves during the budding stage, 15.9 leaves during the flowering stage, and 30.9 leaves during the pod formation stage. These indicators reflect the morphological potential of this variety under natural growing conditions. When the biostimulant “Uz gumin” was applied at a rate of 300 ml/t to seeds, 500 ml/ha during the budding stage, and 800 ml/ha during the flowering stage, a significant increase in the number of leaves was observed in the “Vilana” soybean variety.

Table 1

Effect of biostimulant treatments on the number of leaves formed in soybean varieties (leaves per plant)

Variant number	Soybean varieties	Biostimulant names	Pre-sowing seed treatment rate	Budding stage	During flowering and pod formation	Budding	Flowering	Pod setting stage
1	Nafis	Control	Untreated			4,8	19,5	32,6
2		Uz gumin	300 ml/t	500 ml/ha	800 ml/ha	5,3	21,5	34,0
3		Fitovak	200 ml/t	-	-	5,2	21,0	33,7
4			200 ml/t	300 ml/ha	-	5,6	21,8	34,3
5			200 ml/t	-	500 ml/ha	5,4	22,3	34,9
6			200 ml/t	300 ml/ha	500 ml/ha	5,9	23,0	35,6
7		Yer malhami	2,0 l/t	-	-	5,4	21,6	34,4
8			2,0 l/t	2,0 l/ha	-	5,5	22,5	35,4
9			2,0 l/t	-	2,0 l/ha	5,3	23,4	35,9
10			2,0 l/t	2,0 l/ha	2,0 l/ha	5,9	23,9	36,7
11	Vilana	Control	Untreated			4,1	15,9	30,9
12		Uz gumin	300 ml/t	500 ml/ha	800 ml/ha	4,3	18,4	33,2
13		Fitovak	200 ml/t	-	-	4,2	17,2	32,8
14			200 ml/t	300 ml/ha	-	4,8	19,2	33,6
15			200 ml/t	-	500 ml/ha	4,5	19,9	34,1
16			200 ml/t	300 ml/ha	500 ml/ha	4,7	20,5	35,0
17		Yer malxami	2,0 l/t	-	-	4,4	18,4	33,7
18			2,0 l/t	2,0 l/ha	-	4,9	19,6	34,8
19			2,0 l/t	-	2,0 l/ha	4,6	20,3	35,1
20			2,0 l/t	2,0 l/ha	2,0 l/ha	5,1	21,2	36,6

Specifically, the number of leaves reached 4.3 during the budding stage (0.2 more than the control variant), 18.4 during the flowering stage (2.5 more than the control), and 33.2 during the pod formation stage (2.3 more than the control).

When the “Fitovak” biostimulant was applied only to seeds at a rate of 200 ml/t, noticeable changes were observed. In this variant, the number of leaves reached 4.2 during the budding stage, 17.2 during flowering, and 32.8 during the pod formation stage. Although these results were relatively lower than other combined treatment variants, they still showed an increase compared to the control: 1.9 additional leaves during both the flowering and pod formation stages. Even more positive results were observed when the biostimulant was applied in two stages 200 ml/t to seeds and 300 ml/ha during the budding stage. Under this treatment, 4.8 leaves were formed during budding, 19.2 during flowering, and 33.6 during pod formation. Notably, there was an increase of 3.3 leaves at the flowering stage compared to the control. When the “Fitovak” biostimulant was applied in three stages 200 ml/t to seeds, 300 ml/ha during budding, and 500 ml/ha during the flowering and pod formation stages the results improved significantly. Specifically, 4.7 leaves were observed during budding, 20.5 during flowering, and 35.0 during pod formation.

In the “Vilana” variety, the application of the biopreparation “Yer malhami” also produced positive results. When applied to seeds at a rate of 2.0 l/t, the number of leaves formed was 4.4 during the budding stage, 18.4 during flowering, and 33.7 during pod formation. The best results were recorded when the biostimulant was applied in three stages: 2.0 l/t to seeds, 2.0 l/ha during budding, and 2.0 l/ha during the flowering and pod formation stages. Following the seed treatment and subsequent foliar applications during budding and flowering, the number of leaves increased to 5.1 at the budding stage, 21.2 at flowering, and 36.6 during pod formation.

Conclusion. As a result of field experiments, the influence of various biostimulants and biopreparations on the number of leaves in soybean plants was determined. According to the research findings, the application scheme and timing of the preparations played a significant role in the leaf development of both “Nafis” and “Vilana” varieties. In particular, the application of the biostimulants “Uz gumin” and “Fitovak” to the seeds and during key vegetative growth stages led to a notable increase in leaf number compared to the control. When “Fitovak” was applied at a rate of 200 ml/t to seeds, 300 ml/ha at the budding stage, and 500 ml/ha during the flowering and pod formation stages,

the number of leaves reached 35.6 in the “Nafis” variety and 35.0 in the “Vilana” variety. These figures were significantly higher than those in the untreated control variants, showing an increase of 3.0 to 4.7 leaves. The staged application of the biopreparation “Yer malhami” also showed high efficiency, increasing the number of leaves. Overall, the targeted use of biostimulants and biopreparations proved to be an effective factor in enhancing leaf formation in soybean plants.

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